

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF WAR ON THE ECONOMY AND POST-WAR RECOVERY: THE CASE OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

This research aims to investigate the impact of war and external financing on the welfare and economic activity of a country. The article models the impact of war and external financing (foreign direct investment and external development aid) on a country's welfare (through economic indicators such as employment, inflation, GDP per capita, and export). The results of our empirical analysis demonstrate trends regarding the impact of war and external financing (foreign direct investment and external development aid) on a country's welfare and economic activity. The positive effect of the dummy variable (War) on GDP per capita and export growth can be attributed to increased military spending, reallocation of resources, and economic stimulus. The authors also outline the socioeconomic indicators of Ukraine before and after 2014 (from the Russian occupation of Ukrainian territory and the beginning of Ukraine's Anti-Terrorist Operation). A section of the article is devoted to issues related to the recovery of Ukraine. The discussion highlights the limitations and potential for further research into factors that could enable Ukraine to achieve economic success, despite its security situation in a post-war period.

Keywords: socioeconomic indicators; post-war period; foreign direct investment; external development aid; military spending.

Introduction

After World War II, the biggest wars seemed to belong to the past, and the global community exercised control over conflicts. From the mid-1990s onward, though, there was a trend toward increasing the

number of armed conflicts worldwide. According to the Center for Systemic Peace, 334 armed conflicts were observed from 1945 to 2019 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of military conflicts (1945-2019) by the magnitude of societal-systemic impact [5]

However, no conflicts exceeded the seventh category in terms of intensity. Most of these armed conflicts were wars of independence. Still, some were struggles between communism and democracy, which was typical during the Cold War period, such as the First Indochina War of 1946-1954 and the Korean War of 1950-1953. There was also a tendency to decrease interstate wars.

Every year, we can observe an aggravation in military-political conflicts, accompanied by devastating consequences and increasing instability for the occupied countries. Most conflicts are concentrated in Asia, and the most common types are civil wars and territorial disputes. The UN has found that the most

mutual causes of conflicts today are: regional tensions, rule-of-law violations, illegal economic gain, and resource scarcity exacerbated by climate change. It is worth noting, however, that the economic consequences of political instability, terrorism, and war are entirely different for each country.

Threats of terrorism have increased in France, the United Kingdom, Germany, and Belgium. Consequently, the development of organizational and legal instruments has intensified, and economic, humanitarian, and infrastructural support for countries affected by military conflicts has increased.

The war in Ukraine, which has brought death, destruction, and forced migration, has become a part of Ukraine's reality (Figure 2).

a) humanitarian consequences (as of December 7, 2022) (source: according to [13])

b) civilian victims (as of January 10, 2023) [20]

Figure 2. Russian War in Ukraine: civilian casualties

However, it is already necessary to think about the Ukrainian economy's post-war recovery, which is occurring in cooperation with the international community.

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Literature review

The conducted analysis of the literature reveals a significant interest in studying the causes and consequences of conflicts, including wars. For example,

Coyne and Mathers [9] have analysed several issues regarding the causes of wars and their consequences for countries' economies during post-war periods.

According to Organski & Kugler's [21, 22] study of European countries recovering from the global economic crises caused by the world wars, European countries, during the post-war periods, experienced a trend of economic growth 15-20 years after the end of the wars.

Cerra and Saxena [6] have offered more optimistic conclusions, demonstrating that despite the sharp drop in production after a war, a country's economy rapidly recovers for several years.

However, some studies have focused on the opposite consequences of war for the economy. In this vein, Murdoch and Sandler [18] are convinced that a country's economy does not grow intensively in the first five years after a war.

Collier & Hoeffler [7] notes that during the first five post-conflict years, the probability of recovery of a country's economy is 39%.

Both Wijeweera & Webb [28] and Collier & Hoeffler [7] have substantiated the hypothesis that a country's economy experiences extraordinary growth in a post-war period.

The works of Arrow [1], Lucas [16], Mankiw et al. [17], and Romer [25] analyses the impact of a war

on a country's economic performance and human capital. They developed a growth model, which predicts that the speed of convergence of the post-war economy to the pre-war state depends on the reduction of a country's physical and human capital caused by war.

The rapid economic reconstruction of countries in post-war periods within five years after the war's end is evidenced by the research of Przeworski et al. [23], which emphasizes the influence of the political regime on this process.

Studies show that there is no direct connection between the effects of a war on a country's economy. Still, the neoclassical theory of growth proves that Ukraine's economy can be quickly restored and stabilized after its victory. The recovery period of Ukraine's economy in a post-war period will be affected by the scale of financial and economic losses,

the severity of the destruction of the industrial and infrastructural potential, and its social and communal spheres.

Methods

There are numerous approaches to measuring the economic cost of conflict, and such techniques are developed not only by scientists but also by international and regional organizations [24]. They justify the methods used to measure the damage and losses caused by wars or other destructive events. However, they all cover two main approaches: 1) assessing the direct physical damage and other damage caused by destruction; 2) examining the ramifications of such events on socioeconomic, financial, and other indicators (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Classification of approaches to measuring the economic value of the conflict (source: ourselves)

In our study, the terms of the first approaches will be used under Robinson & Phillips [24] in the following sense: damage – total or partial destruction of physical assets existing in the affected area;1 losses – changes in economic flows arising from the destruction of assets.2

In addition, the first approaches include accounting and analytical methods. To assess the economic consequences of conflict for a country, Gardeazabal [12] recommends using such methods as cost accounting, cross-section methods, time series methods, panel data methods, gravity models, event studies, and natural experiments.

The cost accounting method is based on the country's direct and indirect costs calculation due to the conflict. This method was used by Nordhaus [19] and Davis et al. [10] to estimate the costs of US involvement in the Iraq War. Arunatilake et al. [2] also used it to calculate the cost of the Sri Lankan Civil War.

Results

In 2021, Ukraine celebrated the thirtieth anniversary of its independence. Over the past three decades, it has experienced multiple crises. Starting in 1991, the GDP has declined, and the incomes of Ukrainians have also decreased. However, by the 2000s, the Ukrainian economy had largely been restored. However, 2014, for Ukraine, marked the beginning of an economic shock, as well as an undeclared war that the Russian Federation waged on them, annexing Crimea and occupying Ukraine's Donetsk and Luhansk regions.

This analysis uses panel data of Ukraine for 2006-2021. We reviewed the circumstances of the Ukrainian economy functioning in two terms: pre-war time – eight years 2006-2013; and wartime – eight years 2014-2021.

Nominal GDP makes it possible to summarize the indicators of a country's economic development and characterizes the total production volume, measured in current prices (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Dynamics of Ukraine's nominal GDP from 2006–2021, billion US\$ (source: Authors' calculation based on World Bank Data [29])

The trend in GDP changed between 2006-2013 and 2014-2021, likely due to the war in the country during the latter period. The slope of the regression line for 2006-2013 indicates an average annual increase in GDP per year of 10,191, while the slope of the regression line for 2014-2021 indicates an average yearly increase of 9,0255. This slower GDP growth rate during 2014-2021 compared to 2006-2013 is likely a result of the economic disruptions of the war and reductions in investment caused by it. It is worth noting that wars can have complex and sometimes contradictory effects on a country's economy, and the impact of war on a country's GDP may be influenced

by various other factors as well. Nevertheless, the regression lines suggest that the war in Ukraine likely harmed the economy, leading to a slower GDP growth rate from 2006-2013 and from 2014-2021.

Costalli et al. [8] suggest that during wartime, a country loses an average of 15.7% of its potential GDP per capita. According to Bove et al. [4], the loss is 12.8%.

The dynamics of Ukraine's annual GDP growth shown in Figure 5 demonstrate that in the period of 2006-2013, there was stable GDP growth (except in 2009, as a result of the global financial crisis), but 2014-2021 shows significant periods of decline in Ukraine's GDP.

Figure 5. Ukraine's annual GDP growth from 2006-2021, per billion US\$ (source: Authors' calculation based on World Bank Data [29])

In the State Budget of Ukraine for 2023, GDP has been set at 3.2%, unlike the previous forecast of 4.6% [27].

Empirical research conducted by Bluszcz & Valente [3] has shown that from 2013-2017, the loss of GDP per capita in Ukraine due to the war was 15.1%, and for the Donetsk & Luhansk regions – 47%.

Experts predict that, should warfare end in 2023, Ukraine's GDP level would not reach its pre-war levels until 2026. From 2023 to 2024, the nominal GDP

level of Ukraine is anticipated to be \$130-\$160 billion, with foreign partners providing Ukraine with budget support and financial assistance for infrastructure restoration.

Figure 6 presents the impact of the war on the change in Ukraine's GDP per capita during the pre-war and wartime periods.

Figure 6. Ukraine's GDP per capita, US\$ (source: Authors' calculation based on World Bank Data [29])

The trend of changes in GDP per capita in the studied periods is consistent with the trend of nominal GDP slowdown, which was previously discussed.

The results indicate an increase in GDP per capita from 2006-2008 and from 2010-2013. Indicators for 2015 show a loss of GDP per capita due to warfare in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine, but starting from 2018-2021, this indicator was growing. According to forecasts for 2022, Ukraine's GDP per

capita will decrease, which directly reflects the war's cost.

The dynamics of Ukraine's foreign trade (Figure 7) show a significant acceleration in the growth of both exports and imports of goods and services in the 2006-2008 period (mainly in the export of agricultural, chemical, and metallurgical products, as well as the import of mineral, chemical products, machinery, and equipment).

Figure 7. Ukraine's foreign trade from 2006-2021, per billion US\$ (source: Authors' calculation based on World Bank Data [29])

The global financial and economic crisis of 2008 also affected Ukraine's foreign trade turnover, evidenced by the drop in indicators since 2009, specifically exports by more than 40%, and imports by more than 80% for some goods. From 2010 to 2013, Ukraine's foreign trade indicators grew. However, the 2014-2015 escalation of military conflict destroyed industrial infrastructure facilities and reduced the population's purchasing power and industrial production, leading to a sharp decline in Ukraine's foreign trade in exports and imports. In 2016, the decline phase was replaced by a growth phase, and an increase in Ukrainian exports and imports of goods and services was observed up until 2021.

The analysis of inflation enables policymakers to assess the overall state of the economy during wartime and to identify areas of weakness that may need to be addressed. For example, if inflation is driven by the

rising costs of goods and services, policymakers may need to address supply chain disruptions or other factors that affect the availability of goods and services. In short, inflation analysis provides valuable insights into the state of the economy during wartime, which can be used to guide monetary policy decisions and support overall economic development.

Figure 8 shows slight variations in inflation rates from 2006-2007. The significant increase in inflation in 2008 was due to the global financial crisis, which also affected the economy of Ukraine. However, 2009-2013 demonstrates a decrease in the inflation rate due to the stabilization of the economic situation in Ukraine after the global financial crisis. Since 2014, the inflation rate has increased significantly, but from 2016 the inflation rate gradually decreased (the 2021 COVID-19 pandemic caused the increased inflation rate to return).

Figure 8.

Inflation rate in Ukraine from 2006–2021 in % (source: Authors' calculation based on World Bank Data [29])

The analysis shows that Ukraine's economy encountered a difficult period. However, during 2016–2021, Ukraine's economy seemed to have overcome the worst recession caused by the military conflict with Russia. This recovery lasted until Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022. The consequences of these events are currently difficult to imagine and predict.

Discussion

Donetsk (25%), Kharkiv (18%), Luhansk (13%), Mykolayivsk (9%), and Zaporizhia (7%) are the regions of Ukraine most affected by military operations,

comprising most of the damage and destruction in monetary terms (%), followed by the Kyiv (7%) and Chernihiv (6%) regions [11].

The Kyiv School of Economics has estimated Ukraine's direct losses due to the war at \$108.3 billion [14].

The assessment of Ukraine's losses from the war with Russia, as well as Ukraine's need to restore destroyed and damaged assets, is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Direct damage to infrastructure and indirect losses to the economy due to Russia's military aggression in Ukraine, per billion US\$ (source: Authors' calculation based on [14, 15])

As of September 1, 2022, there has been a total of \$127 billion in asset losses. More than a third of it was due to damage to the housing stock (39.7%). In all, 7.3% of the total area of the housing stock of Ukraine, which is home to about 1.2 million households (about 3 million people), was damaged (destroyed). Significant damage was caused to infrastructure (27.8%), assets of enterprises and industry (7.8%), education (5.5%), the agro-industrial sector, and land resources (5.2%).

The largest share of the overall damage is the destroyed housing. According to the latest data, the Russian invaders have destroyed and damaged at least 129,900 residential buildings, specifically 114,700 private houses and 15,100 apartment buildings. The

damage to high-rise buildings amounts to \$42.3 billion. Owners of private homes have lost another \$5.4 billion. Infrastructural losses are the second largest, with the war resulting in losses amounting to \$31.6 billion. Businesses and industries have lost \$8.8 billion due to the conflict. As of July 27, 2022, the Russian army in Ukraine has destroyed 2,217 educational institutions (worth \$3.8 billion), 903 medical institutions (worth \$1.6 billion), and 89 social institutions (worth more than \$300 million).

On July 4-5, 2022, Lugano, Switzerland, hosted the Ukraine Recovery Conference, which was attended by 40 countries and 20 international organizations. The "Declaration of Lugano" provides a plan for the post-war reconstruction of Ukraine within ten years (the first stage from 2023-2025; the second

stage from 2025-2032). This plan includes 17 programs and 850 projects, with a total cost of \$750 billion (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Main areas of funding in the Ukraine Recovery Program, per billion US\$ (source: compiled by the authors using [26])

In the first stage, the recovery program should thus focus on restoring destroyed housing and critical infrastructure (roads, railways, airports, harbours, etc.), as well as providing employment support and social support, including providing humanitarian aid (food, medicines, etc.). In the long term, the recovery program should be focused on the radical modernization of Ukraine, particularly in terms of institutional reforms (judicial reform, civil service reform) to bring legislation and relevant institutions closer to European standards. All these reforms are essential for the successful economic transformation of Ukraine.

Conclusions

The level of state power is a determining factor in the availability and efficacy of resources used and in the development of democracy, human capital, and other non-tangible factors that can enable a country to become economically prosperous. The country's economic development directly affects its defence capability – and, therefore, the ability and development of its military potential.

This analysis has revealed some controversial trends. In particular, the dummy variable (war) positively affects GDP per capita and export growth. It can be attributed to increased military spending, the reallocation of resources, and economic stimulus:

1. War often increases government spending on defence and military operations, boosting economic activity. The military sector can be an essential source of employment, generating demand for goods and services, resulting in higher economic output and high

GDP per capita. In addition, military spending can lead to the development of new technologies and innovations, which can spill over into the civilian sector, further stimulating the economy.

2. War results in reallocating resources from non-military to military sectors, improving productivity and competitiveness in the military industry. It can lead to higher exports of military goods and services and the development of new technologies and innovations that can be commercialised and exported. The reallocation of resources can also increase efficiency in the military sector, reducing the cost of military goods and services and making them more competitive in the international market.

3. War catalyses economic stimulus through increased government spending on public works projects, such as infrastructure development. It can generate employment and boost demand for goods and services, leading to higher economic output and, as a result, GDP per capita. Additionally, developing new infrastructure increases the economy's efficiency and makes it more competitive, stimulating exports and contributing to long-term economic growth.

We also found a positive effect of foreign direct investment and external development assistance on GDP growth per capita and exports. Modelling the influence of independent variables on inflation did not yield statistically significant results.

In general, the impact of war on economic indicators can be complex and vary greatly depending on the war's specific circumstances and the war and the

country's domestic economy. While war can positively affect the economy in the short term, it also results in negative consequences, such as reduced investment, decreased consumer spending, and lower economic growth in the long term. The effects of war are challenging and destructive, but the onset of peace is always accompanied by gradual economic and social recovery.

This research indicates a significant drop in GDP per capita in Ukraine since 2014, an inevitable consequence of the war. The pre-war period was characterised by economic growth for Ukraine, but there was a significant deterioration in all indicators during the war.

A period of economic and social recovery awaits Ukraine after the victory. It will depend on the nation's cultural, geopolitical, and economic features. For post-war Ukraine, the main focus should be restoring energy-generating capacities and transport infrastructure (bridges, railway junctions, airports) to enable industrial production and the reconstruction of housing stock. It has highlighted the issue of a catastrophic labour shortage since people are currently being forced to move abroad or to rural areas with no job prospects. However, the post-war reconstruction of Ukraine should also be aimed at a radical change in the economy's structure, a transition from an agricultural or raw material type to an industrial-innovative one based on creating a modern, high-tech, digitalised industry.

Further research should focus on developing a model for the recovery of the Ukrainian economy by determining the priorities of state policy and updating sectoral and regional strategies aimed at creating and developing industrial and technological parks on the territory of Ukraine to produce and export high-tech products.

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